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**THE USE OF PALM KERNEL SHELL AS PARTIAL REPLACEMENT FOR
COARSE AGGREGATE IN CONCRETE**

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ABSTRACT

The effect of palm kernel shells as partial replacement for coarse aggregate in concrete on strength and density was investigated. Palm kernel shell was used to replace 10, 20 and 30% by weight of granite stone in concrete made with a water-to-cement ratio of 0.4 and 0.6. Compressive strength and density of the concrete were determined for each of the replacement levels. The density of the concrete thus produced was within the range for normal weight concrete (2300 – 2500 kg/m³). Compressive strength increased with increasing age but reduced with increasing palm kernel shell content. Compressive strength of between 20 and 36 MPa was recorded for the replacement levels and water-to-cement ratios studied.

KEYWORDS: Palm kernel shell; concrete; compressive strength; density

INTRODUCTION

The utilization of non-conventional construction materials requires an understanding of their properties solely and in combination with conventional ones to enhance their acceptability and achieve sustainability with respect to their development and subsequent utilisation. The utilisation of conventional construction materials most especially cement and aggregates for concrete production have been associated with greenhouse gas emissions and environmental degradation due to the exploitation of non-renewable natural resources. Concrete production rely heavily on non-renewable natural materials and as such have a significant impact on the environment. To this effect, the use of some industrial and agricultural wastes have been advocated and researched to certain extent for use in the production of structural grade concrete. Palm kernel shells (PKS), an agricultural waste is a non-conventional material which has been investigated to certain extent as lightweight aggregate in the production of structural concrete (Itam et al., 2016; Oyejobi et al., 2012; Yew et al., 2014).

Most studies on PKS often investigate its use in the production of light weight aggregate concrete. The use of PKS in structural light weight concrete is based on the availability of the PKS, its material properties and economy. PKS is known to have good fire resistance and its particle size is greatly affected by the processing method. While a fraction of the PKS is utilised as fuel for cooking, a substantial amount is either burnt in open air or piled up in open fields even though it does not decompose easily. According to the commission for environmental cooperation (CEC) report (2014), open air burning of agricultural waste results in emission of pollutants (particulate matters and gases) which pose a threat to both human and animal health. Also, the leachates from burning or decomposed waste sites can contaminate both surface

and ground water thereby making it unsafe for direct consumption. This may further require expensive techniques to purify the water to make it safe. Hence, since these wastes need to be disposed of, there is a dire need for safe, cost effective, efficient and sustainable disposal methods. The utilisation of this waste in concrete production as whole or partial substitute for aggregates offers the advantage of improving the thermal properties as well as reducing cost while reducing the dependence on non-renewable aggregates.

Yew et al. (2014) investigated the effect of age and species of palm tree from which PKS was obtained and the particle size of PKS on the properties of light weight concrete. The study showed that by incorporating silica fume in the mix, the strength of PKS concrete can be increased without including conventional coarse aggregate. The study also reported that older palm trees produces harder shells which contributes to the strength of PKS lightweight concrete. For such older palm tree shells, a 28 day compressive strength of 55 MPa was reported. Maghfouri et al. (2018) attempted to investigate the optimum quantity of PKS for the reduction in the associated drying shrinkage of PKS lightweight aggregate concrete. A high compressive strength ranging between 40 MPa and 64 MPa was recorded for substitution levels of between 20% and 100% PKS. The study reported that PKS content between 20% and 60% may control the drying shrinkage. The study of Idah & Musa (2010) showed that the replacement of granite with PKS produces lightweight concrete. The study uses a mix ratio of 1:2:4 which is used for structural concrete. The compressive strength recorded was less than 10 MPa for all replacement levels investigated.

Oyejobi et al. (2012) used nominal mixes 1:1.5:3, 1:2:4, 1:3:6 and 1:4:8 and w/c of 0.38 to prepare concrete containing palm kernel shell and only mix proportion 1:1.5:3 gave a structural grade strength of 20 N/mm², other mixes investigated gave poor strength result. Also, Olanipekun et al. (2006) studied nominal mix 1:1:2 and 1:2:4 and replacement levels ranging from 25-100% using a w/c of 0.5 and 0.75. The study found that the density decreased with increase in PKS content and with increase in mix ratio. Also, compressive strength decreases with increasing PKS content and that concrete grade 20 MPa and 15 MPa can be produced with PKS content up to 50%. By using the DOE mix design method and replacing granite with PKS from 25% to 100%, Itam et al. (2016) recorded a compressive strength of 30.2 MPa at 28 days of curing with subsequent reduction in strength with increasing PKS content. Also, the water absorption was shown to increase with increase in PKS content but was within standard range. The influence of curing methods on the compressive strength of palm kernel shell concrete was studied by Odeyemi et al. (2021) using a mix ratio of 1:1:2 and w/c of 0.5. The curing method studied were water curing, water sprinkling, wet curing with sawdust and open air curing. For all the curing methods, the compressive strength increases with curing age while open air curing gave the least 28 days compressive strength of 13.11 MPa for a target strength of 15 MPa.

From the foregoing, the use of nominal mix limits the strength that can be attained by PKS concrete while the density obtained mostly falls within the range for light weight concrete. This study investigates the effect of the use of palm kernel shell as lightweight aggregate and as partial replacement of coarse aggregate in concrete production using a designed mix. PKS was used alongside granite as coarse aggregate to study the properties and its potential use in production of structural concrete.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The Portland cement used was a CEM 1 42.5 N which conforms to the requirement of BS EN 197-1:2000. The PKS used was collected from a local mill while granite of size 19 mm was used as the coarse aggregate. The fine aggregate used was a river bed sand air dried in the laboratory to surface dry condition. The concrete was designed using the concrete and cement Institute (CCI) method (Fulton, 2009) which allowed for adjustment of the materials relative density based on percentage content in the mix. The concrete was prepared using w/c ratios of 0.4 and 0.6 and was hand mixed. The cement content for 0.4 w/c was 525 kg/m³ and for 0.6 it was 350 kg/m³. No adjustment was made in the water content used for the preparation of concrete. 100 mm concrete cubes were cast and demoulded after 2 hours of casting and were subsequently stored in water till testing date. The compressive strength and density were determined at 3, 7 and 28 days of curing.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Effects of PKS content on density of concrete

The replacement of granite with PKS has an effect on the density of the concrete. The percentage reduction in density of the moist cubes compared to 0% PKS at 10 % and 20% was about 4% and 5% while at 30% PKS content, it was about 12%. The density of the cubes at 28 days of curing for 0% PKS and 0.4 w/c was 2600 kg/m³ while for 10%, 20% and 30% PKS content, it was 2500 kg/m³, 2470 kg/m³ and 2300 kg/m³ respectively. For 0.6 w/c, the density of the cubes at 0, 10, 20 and 30% was 2500, 2400, 2300 and 2300 kg/m³ respectively. The densities recorded in this study are within the density range for normal weight concrete according to BS EN 206-1:2000. Itam et al. (2016) recorded a density of 1960 kg/m³ at 25% PKS content using the DOE mix design method. Generally, studies which used nominal mix e.g. (Okpala, 1990), recorded densities lesser than 2000 kg/m³. There is an improvement in the density of concrete obtained showing that designing a mix for concrete containing PKS has an advantage and that PKS may be used to produce both normal and light weight concrete depending on the percentage replacement and mix proportioning method adopted. The result obtained is different from other studies which recorded densities within the range of lightweight concrete i.e. densities lesser than 2000 kg/m³. The difference lies in the mix proportioning method adopted, the differences in w/c ratio and likely the target strength. Although, the PKS was a light weight material itself, its use alongside a conventional coarse aggregate up to 30% content produces a normal weight concrete.

Figure 1: Variation of compressive strength with PKS content at 0.4 w/c

Figure 2: Variation of compressive strength with PKS content at 0.6 w/c

Effects of percentage replacement level on compressive strength

The result presented in Figures 1 and 2 showed that for a given w/c ratio, the compressive strength varies with percentage PKS content in the mix. Compressive strength reduces with increasing substitution level. For 10% replacement level, the percentage reduction varied between 7.9% and 39% when compared to 0% PKS samples for the curing ages investigated. The 20% replacement showed a percentage reduction of between 16% and 34% while 30% replacement level showed a percentage reduction of between 19% and 49%. Also, for a given replacement level, the compressive strength varied with w/c. The target strength was 30MPa, for 10 and 20% replacement levels at 0.4 w the 28 day strength recorded were 31.33 MPa and 36.43 MPa respectively.

When compared to studies which used nominal mixes, e.g. (Odeyemi et al., 2021; Olanipekun et al., 2006; Oyejobi et al., 2012), the strength reported rarely reach 30MPa at 28 days of curing. The reduction in strength can be linked to the differences in the specific gravity of the two coarse aggregate used, although this is a limitation but the result showed that up to 20% and based on the compressive strength recorded, PKS can be used in structural grade concrete. Another contributory factor to the strength reduction is the differences in the surface property between the two coarse aggregate. The surface of PKS is smoother and adhesion to cement paste is expected to be reduced compared to the granite surface and this has an implication on the transition zone. Also, is the fact that PKS inclusion do not affect the hydration of cement as there is strength gain at each of the replacement levels up to the 28 days investigated.

CONCLUSION

The partial substitution of granite with untreated PKS in concrete up to 30% was investigated. The density of the concrete produced was within the density range for normal weight concrete as the densities were higher than 2000 kg/m³. Also, compressive strength decreases with increase in PKS content but increases with increasing curing age for a particular w/c ratio. The compressive strength recorded for both w/c ratio investigated falls within the range of 20 -36 MPa, as a result, PKS up to 30% may be used alongside granite in the production of structural grade concrete.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest associated with the work presented in this article.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data on which this work is based may be made available upon reasonable request

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